

PRODUCTIVITY ASSESSMENT AND FACTORS INFLUENCING IT IN THE REPUBLIC OF ARMENIA

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the multi-dimensional aspects of industrial productivity, focusing primarily on its estimation methods and the factors influencing it. It delves into different productivity measurement approaches such as partial, total, and total factor productivity. A significant portion of the research is dedicated to assessing the impact of various macroeconomic factors on productivity, with a special focus on the Armenian economy. The findings highlight the complex interplay between productivity and factors like GDP growth, investment growth, price competitiveness, inflow of foreign capital, external demand, and macroeconomic policy, providing insightful implications for industrial policy and strategic planning. The main results demonstrate that variables such as government investment, exchange rate, foreign demand significantly impact productivity, with noticeable variations across different industrial sectors.

Keywords: industrial productivity, Productivity Assessment, TFP, capital stock estimation, Armenian economy.

Introduction

Industrial productivity serves as a cornerstone of economic analysis, influencing a country's competitiveness, living standards, and overall economic health. The concept of productivity, while deceptively simple, encompasses a wide range of interpretations and metrics, each providing unique insights into the efficiency and effectiveness of industrial output. The importance of understanding and enhancing industrial productivity cannot be overstated, especially in developing economies where resource allocation and efficient production are pivotal for sustainable growth. This research is an endeavor to dissect and understand the intricate fabric of industrial productivity, with a particular focus on the factors influencing it. We explore different avenues of productivity measurement, including partial, total factor, and total productivity approaches, and how these methodologies can be applied and interpreted in various industrial contexts.

The primary objectives of this research are to estimate productivity in industrial subsectors and to identify the key determinants of industrial productivity in Armenia and to understand the impact of these determinants on different industrial sectors. The research questions revolve around the efficacy of current productivity measurement methods, the role of governmental policies and economic reforms in shaping industrial productivity, and the potential for technological innovations to drive productivity gains. The study delves into macroeconomic factors such as government policies, international trade dynamics, and economic reforms, and uses econometric tools to estimate the significance of these factors for productivity growth.

The findings of this research are expected to provide valuable insights for policymakers, industrialists, and academicians, aiding in the formulation of strategies to enhance industrial productivity. The study not

only contributes to the academic discourse on productivity analysis but also offers practical implications for industrial policy and strategic planning in Armenia and similar economies.

Literature review

Although in the professional literature there are a number of analysis dedicated to the importance of productivity and the methodology of its estimation, there are not many works discussing the factors affecting productivity and the steps necessary to increase it, which causes the need for more detailed study of these issues. Even the definition of the term "productivity" has various forms in different authors' works. Thomas G. (2004) describes the definition of productivity as simple and complex at the same time, reasoning that with both a technical and managerial concept [20]. Productivity estimation methods, however, have already been developed to some extent, and there are some acceptable approaches to productivity estimation at the macro level.

The estimation of productivity is commonly distinguished into three dimensions [13]

- Partial productivity, which is the productivity of a specific production factor, i.e. labor or capital,
- Total factor productivity, that shows how productive the labor and capital are together,
- Total productivity considers other production factors (material, energy and others) as well.

The above methods mainly focus on the evaluation of productivity at the macro level, while the implementation of evaluations at the micro level, i.e. using data from organizations, is considered somewhat problematic given the data availability and difficulties in getting the representative samples. There are other types of classifications of productivity measurements as well, which are concentrated on measurement of productivity of a single organization. Sink & Tuttle (1989) classified

them as: partial-factor, total-factor, and surrogate measures, which are used by public or private organizations [17].

One of the most comprehensive methods of productivity estimation is considered the Multifactor Productivity Measurements Model [22] suggested by Wazed, M. & Ahmed, S. (2008). It comprises nine components, including output quantity, input quantity, revenue, output price, cost, profits, productivity itself, etc. There are other methods developed to estimate productivity in company level (Goshu Y.Y., Kitaw D., Matebu A. (2017)) [8],

The relationship between macroeconomic factors and industrial productivity has been extensively explored in economic literature. Scholars like Solow (1957) laid the foundation for understanding the role of technological progress in productivity growth, arguing that technological advancement is a key driver of increased output per unit of input [18]. This view is complemented by Romer (1990), who emphasized the significance of human capital and knowledge in spurring technological innovation and, consequently, productivity [16]. More recent studies, such as those by Acemoglu and Robinson (2012), have highlighted the impact of political and institutional structures on economic performance, suggesting that inclusive economic institutions foster productivity growth by encouraging investment in new technologies and skills [1]. In terms of specific macroeconomic variables, Barro (1991) and Mankiw, Romer, and Weil (1992) have shown that government policies, education levels, and capital investments play a substantial role in determining productivity levels [4] [14]. Furthermore, Hall and Jones (1999) argue that the social infrastructure of a country, encompassing aspects like property rights and political stability, significantly influences its productivity [9]. These perspectives collectively underscore the multifaceted nature of macroeconomic factors influencing productivity, ranging from technological innovation and human capital to institutional frameworks and government policies.

Recent studies continue to expand our understanding of the interplay between macroeconomic factors and productivity. A key focus in contemporary research is on the impact of globalization and trade policies. Autor, Dorn, and Hanson (2016), for instance, provide insights into the effects of trade exposure on local labor markets and productivity, emphasizing the transformative role of international trade in shaping industrial output [3]. Another pivotal area is the influence of digitalization and technological adoption, as discussed by Brynjolfsson, Rock, and Syverson (2017), who explore the paradox of productivity slowdown amidst rapid technological advancement, a phenomenon often termed as the "productivity paradox" [5]. Furthermore, the role of macroeconomic stability and fiscal policies has been highlighted by Aghion, Hemous, and Kharroubi (2014), who examine how different fiscal policies can either hinder or promote productivity growth, especially in the face of economic shocks [2]. The importance of environmental factors has also gained prominence, as demonstrated by Dinda (2004) and Stokey (2020), who discuss how sustainable practices and environmental regulations can impact industrial

productivity [6] [19]. Lastly, the effect of labor market dynamics on productivity cannot be understated. As shown by Michaels, Natraj, and Van Reenen (2014), labor market reforms and human capital development are critical in enhancing productivity, particularly in the context of rapidly evolving industrial landscapes [15]. The work dedicated to the identification of factors affecting productivity in the RA economy was carried out by M. Shahinyan [23], in 2022, the results of which showed that changes in productivity are significantly influenced by physical and human capital, natural resources, and imports of goods and services.

The estimation of productivity

Productivity assessment was carried out in several ways according to the logic of the three types productivity mentioned above. In particular, initially the factor productivity was estimated for the Armenian economy, which eventually is the productivity of labor and capital (TFP). For that purpose, Cobb-Douglas production function was used.

$$Y = A * K^{\alpha} * L^{1-\alpha}$$

From where total factor productivity is estimated as follows

$$A = \frac{Y}{K^{\alpha} * L^{1-\alpha}}$$

Where A is the TFP, K is the stock of capital, L is the labor supply and α is the share of capital in output: In this method, it is essential to estimate productivity what assumptions are made for the estimation of α . In our case, the value of α 0.6 was used in the estimations, based on the share of gross profit and gross mixed income in the added value, which was 60% in the last five years (2017-2022).

The time series of capital stock was estimated by the capital accumulation formula as follows.

$$K_t = \delta * K_{t-1} + I_t$$

Where δ is the amortization rate, and I_t represents capital investment at time t : However, to make calculations using the above formula, it is necessary to have the initial amount of capital, the rate of growth of which can then be calculated using data on investments and amortization.

To calculate the initial stock of capital, the simple methods known in the literature were used [10] [7] [11] [12], which are based on the subtraction of the capital weight formula from the formula of capital accumulation, as a result of which the initial stock of capital is calculated by the following formula.

$$K_{is} = \frac{s(1+g)}{\delta+g}$$

Where K_{is} is the initial level of capital stock, as a percent of GDP, s is the share of savings (or investment) to GDP and g is the real GDP growth rate. For the latters, the average values of the last 10 years (2013-2022) were used, which are 18.9% for s , and 4.2% for economic growth. The rate of amortization was adopted at 5%, based on the indicator frequently used in professional literature. Based on these data, the initial weight of capital in GDP was estimated at 2.14%.

The results of the assessments are presented in Figures 1 and 2. It can be noted that the economic growth in RA was significantly related to the growth of productivity, which is evidenced by the similar trends of these indicators over time.

Figure 1. Real GDP and TFP, real growth rates, %

Figure 2. Real GDP and TFP, index

Source: Statistical committee of the Republic of Armenia, authors' calculations

Then, in order to make the estimations more comprehensive, the productivity according to the sectors of the economy was also evaluated. However, as sectoral data on investment and depreciation are not available, partial labor productivity was estimated instead of TFP.

Figure 3. Labor productivity in different sectors of industry

Source: Statistical committee of the Republic of Armenia, authors' calculations

The results of the assessment of sectoral productivity, representing the ratio of the real value added of the sector and the number of people employed in that sector, are presented in Figure 3. In general, the productivity in all subsectors of the RA industry had a significant increase, but the increase in the productivity of the mining industry stands out. In 2021, the latter increased by about 2.6 times over the previous 10 years, and compared to 2003, by about 5.6 times, while the productivity of the industry in general increased twice. The productivity growth of the manufacturing industry is lower than the productivity growth of both the mining industry and the general industry, growing 1.4 times

(by about 38%) over the previous 10 years, and by 1.9 times (by about 94%) compared to 2003.

In order to have a more comprehensive understanding of productivity and its dynamics, it is also necessary to identify its main drivers. For this, both macro-level and micro-data-based assessments need to be carried out. In this work, the identification and analysis of factors affecting productivity at the macro level was mainly emphasized, and the analysis at the level of organizations is planned to be carried out in the later stages of this research.

Factors affecting productivity

Productivity is a multifaceted phenomenon by nature, and almost all factors, including economic and

non-economic factors can affect it. In this work, an attempt was made to identify the macroeconomic factors and processes that had a significant impact on the productivity of industry in RA. For this purpose, a number of macroeconomic factors were identified, which were divided into groups:

- Domestic factors: real GDP growth, investment growth
- Factors characterizing price competitiveness: real and nominal effective exchange rates, bilateral exchange rates
- Indicators characterizing the inflow of foreign capital: remittances, FDI
- External demand: weighted average GDP of partner countries, export volumes
- Fiscal policy: increase in public spending and public investment

Linear regression models were built to evaluate the effects of the above indicators. At the same time, the evaluations were carried out both for the productivity of the general industry and for the productivity of individual branches of the industry.

Estimation results

The evaluation of the factors affecting the productivity of the industry as a whole was carried out using regression analysis, the results of which are presented in Table 1 in Appendix. The effects of all the above factors on productivity were evaluated, but not all of them were statistically significant. Specifically, among the evaluated factors, a significant positive relationship was observed between government capital expenditures and industrial productivity. Estimates show that acceleration of the growth rate of government capital expenditures by one percentage point can lead to an increase in the productivity of the industrial sector by about 0.02 percentage points. This result is consistent with the results of scientific works on the evaluation of the effects of capital expenditure on economic growth [21].

The factors affecting productivity in the manufacturing sector are different from those that we saw analyzing the industry sector as a whole. If in the case of

the general industry the external demand and the exchange rate did not have a significant effect, then in the case of the manufacturing they become particularly important. Moreover, among several types of exchange rates (effective, two-way, real and nominal, which were used when evaluating the models), the nominal exchange rate was the most significant. Thus, one-unit nominal depreciation of AMD leads to an increase in productivity by around 0.5 percentage points. Changes in external demand also affect the productivity of the manufacturing sector. An increase in foreign demand of one percentage point leads to an acceleration of productivity growth by 1.9 percentage points (see Table 2 in the Appendix).

The results of estimations show that changes in productivity in the mining sector are less explainable by macroeconomic factors. The international prices of copper and other metals were also used in the evaluations, but no significant relationship between them and the productivity of the mining industry was found. A significant effect is observed only with the exchange rate (see Table 3 in the Appendix), and the relationship is as expected, that is, the depreciation of the exchange rate leads to an increase in productivity.

Conclusions

The research concludes that productivity in different industrial subsectors had different dynamics and was driven by different factors. Significant findings include the impact of government capital expenditures on industrial productivity, indicating that increased government spending can positively influence industrial output. The study also reveals distinct influences on different sectors, such as the manufacturing and mining sectors, where factors like exchange rates and external demand play pivotal roles. In particular, the external demand and the exchange rate are significant factors in case of manufacturing, while for productivity in mining sector the most significant factor is nominal exchange rate. These insights underscore the importance of tailored economic policies to foster productivity growth. Future research directions are suggested, including a deeper dive into micro-data-based assessments and a more nuanced analysis of sector-specific productivity drivers.

Annex

Table 1.

The results of estimating the effects of different factors on industrial productivity

Dependent Variable: D(L_PROD_IND)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 10/23/23 Time: 00:25

Sample (adjusted): 2005Q2 2021Q4

Included observations: 67 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(L_PROD_IND(-1))	-0.466018	0.099575	-4.680051	0.0000
D(L_GOV_CAP_EXP)	0.015408	0.006882	2.238921	0.0287
D(L_TFP)	0.393388	0.147563	2.665894	0.0097
C	0.011515	0.005750	2.002481	0.0495
R-squared	0.410020	Mean dependent var		0.009733
Adjusted R-squared	0.381926	S.D. dependent var		0.058842
S.E. of regression	0.046260	Akaike info criterion		-3.251220
Sum squared resid	0.134821	Schwarz criterion		-3.119597
Log likelihood	112.9159	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-3.199137
F-statistic	14.59442	Durbin-Watson stat		1.912759
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Table 2.

The results of estimating the effects of different factors on productivity of manufacturing sector

Dependent Variable: D(L_PROD_MANUF)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 10/23/23 Time: 01:31

Sample (adjusted): 2006Q1 2021Q4

Included observations: 64 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(L_PROD_MANUF(-1))	-0.322356	0.103335	-3.119539	0.0028
D(L_USD(-3))	0.475186	0.171590	2.769314	0.0075
D(L_FD_INDEX(-3))	1.914005	0.659155	2.903727	0.0052
D(L_TFP(-1))	-0.560342	0.188506	-2.972536	0.0042
R-squared	0.387497	Mean dependent var		0.010778
Adjusted R-squared	0.356872	S.D. dependent var		0.075280
S.E. of regression	0.060371	Akaike info criterion		-2.716165
Sum squared resid	0.218677	Schwarz criterion		-2.581235
Log likelihood	90.91729	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.663009
Durbin-Watson stat	2.139247			

Table 3.

The results of estimating the effects of different factors on productivity of mining sector

Dependent Variable: D(L_PROD_MINING)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 09/08/23 Time: 10:10

Sample (adjusted): 2003Q3 2021Q4

Included observations: 74 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(L_PROD_MINING(-1))	-0.254570	0.112714	-2.258543	0.0270
D(L_USD(-3))	0.925699	0.438003	2.113455	0.0381
C	0.028940	0.014838	1.950418	0.0551
R-squared	0.109435	Mean dependent var		0.022260
Adjusted R-squared	0.084348	S.D. dependent var		0.131267
S.E. of regression	0.125609	Akaike info criterion		-1.271585
Sum squared resid	1.120217	Schwarz criterion		-1.178177
Log likelihood	50.04863	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-1.234323
F-statistic	4.362325	Durbin-Watson stat		2.038696
Prob(F-statistic)	0.016336			

References

1. Acemoglu, D., & Robinson, J. A. (2012). *Why Nations Fail: The Origins of Power, Prosperity, and Poverty*. Crown Publishers.
2. Aghion, P., Hemous, D., & Kharroubi, E. (2014). Credit Constraints, Cyclical Fiscal Policy and Industry Growth. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 62, 41-58.
3. Autor, D. H., Dorn, D., & Hanson, G. H. (2016). The China Shock: Learning from Labor Market Adjustment to Large Changes in Trade. *Annual Review of Economics*, 8, 205-240.
4. Barro, R. J. (1991). Economic Growth in a Cross Section of Countries. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 106(2), 407-443.
5. Brynjolfsson, E., Rock, D., & Syverson, C. (2017). Artificial Intelligence and the Modern Productivity Paradox: A Clash of Expectations and Statistics. NBER Working Paper No. 24001.
6. Dinda, S. (2004). Environmental Kuznets Curve Hypothesis: A Survey. *Ecological Economics*, 49(4), 431-455.
7. Fuente, A. d., & Domenech, R. (2000). Human Capital in Growth Regressions: How Much Difference Does Data Quality Make? Economics Department Working Paper, 262, OECD, Paris
8. Goshu Y.Y., Kitaw D., Matebu A. (2017) "Development of Productivity Measurement and Analysis Framework for Manufacturing Companies", *Journal of Optimization in Industrial Engineering* 22 (2017) 1-13, DOI: 10.22094/joie.2017.274
9. Hall, R. E., & Jones, C. I. (1999). Why Do Some Countries Produce So Much More Output Per Worker Than Others? *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 114(1), 83-116.
10. Harberger, A. C. (1978). *Perspectives on Capital and Technology in Less Developed Countries*. M. J. Artis and A. R. Nobay, eds., *Contemporary Economic Analysis*, London.
11. Jacob, V., Sharma, S. C., & Grabowsky, R. (1997). Capital Stock Estimates for Major Esctors and Disaggregated Manufacturing in Selected OECD Countries. *Applied Economics*, 29, pp. 563-579.
12. Kamps, C. (2006). New Estimates of Government Net Capital Stocks for 22 OECD Countries 1960-2001. *IMF Staff Paper*, 53 (1), pp. 120-150
13. Kendrick, J. W. (1961). *Productivity Trends in United States for NBER*. New York: Princeton University Press, Princeton.
14. Mankiw, N. G., Romer, D., & Weil, D. N. (1992). A Contribution to the Empirics of Economic Growth. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 107(2), 407-437.
15. Michaels, G., Natraj, A., & Van Reenen, J. (2014). Has ICT Polarized Skill Demand? Evidence from Eleven Countries over 25 years. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 96(1), 60-77.
16. Romer, P. M. (1990). Endogenous Technological Change. *Journal of Political Economy*, 98(5), S71-S102.
17. Sink, D. & Tuttle, T. (1989). *Planning and measurement of in your organisation of the future*. Norcross, USA: Industrial Engineering and Management Press
18. Solow, R. M. (1957). Technical Change and the Aggregate Production Function. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 39(3), 312-320.
19. Stokey, N. L. (2020). Catching Up and Falling Behind: The Impact of Climate Change on Economic Growth. *Econometrica*, 88(4), 1591-1624.

20. Thomas, G. (2004). Performance Improvement towards a Method for Finding and Prioritizing Potential Performance Improvement Areas in Manufacturing Operations. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 53(1), pp. 52-71.

21. Petrosyan G. et al "Assessment of the effects of public investment on GDP growth: case of Armenia", *Science of Europe*, No 78 (2021) Vol. 2, Praha, Czech Republic, 2021, pp. 46-60

22. Wazed, M. & Ahmed, S. (2008). Multifactor Productivity Measurements Model (MFPMM) as Effectual Performance Measures in Manufacturing. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), pp. 987-996.

23. Shahinyan M, Analysis of RA industry productivity factors, *Scientific Artsakh*, № 1(12), 2022